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Whole Body Antioxidant Status of Silver Carp Fingerlings Fed Diet Containing Various Dietary Organic Acids

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ABSTRACT

A 10-week feeding trial was conducted to evaluate the whole-body antioxidant status of silver carp fingerlings when fed with diets containing various organic acids. Five experimental diets were formulated, such as D₁ containing no supplemented organic acids, while D₂ contain (2%malic acid), D₃ (2%citric acid), D₄ (2% formic acid) and D₅ (2% lactic acid). During the experiment, water quality parameters including temperature, pH and DO were controlled. Results showed that acidification of diet significantly reduced the activity of SOD, CAT and GPX throughout the body of silver carp fingerlings. Moreover, among different organic acid groups, the maximum value was observed in citric acid while, minimum value was recorded in formic acid. Data on whole-body antioxidant enzymes were subjected to one-way analysis of variance following Steel *et al.* (1996). Differences between among means were compared by Tukey's Honestly Significant Difference Test and considered significant at (p<0.05) (Snedecor and Conhran, 1991).

INTRODUCTION

The global aquaculture industry currently produces 45% of all seafood that is consumed all over the world. It has been estimated that it will be increased by 75% in the next 20 years (FTU, 2007). In Egypt, aquaculture accounts for 60% of total fish production sources (GAFRD, 2007). Essential nutrients are not enough to fulfill the demand of the high quality feeds so complementary feed additives are needed to improve efficiency of feed utilization and survival rates of fish.

Among them, short chain organic acids are mainly used as they have beneficial effects on feed preservation and utilization (Luckstadt, 2006; Atapattu and Senevirathne, 2013; Sing *et al.*, 2014). Organic acid supplementation in fish diet reduces the gastric pH (Baruah *et al.*, 2005) which leads to increase the absorption of nutrients (Boling- Frankenbach *et al.*, 2001) and also help in the breakdown of phytate (Jongbloed, 1987), so it is easily available to fish. Moreover, it also decreases the gastric emptying rate by dietary acidification (Mayer, 1994). Furthermore, it also improves the gut health of animal as they have antagonistic effect on microbes (Ravindran and Kornegay, 1993; Partanen and Mroz, 1999).

Organic acid increases the availability of dietary minerals through acidification in several ways. Firstly, by the modification of mineral transport mechanism by changing the stomach acidity. Secondly, supplementation of organic acid in the diet acts as a chelating agent and affects the complex forming ability of elements (Ravindran and Kornegay, 1993). Thirdly, the absorption area for minerals is increased (Baruah *et al.*, 2007a) through the proliferation of the epithelial cells in gastrointestinal mucosa (Sakata *et al.*, 1995) by the inclusion of organic

acid in the diet.

CA, one of organic acid is widely used for acidification of diet as it has unique flavor and high buffering capacity (Hossain *et al.*, 2007). It has a great potential to reduce the antagonistic interactions between trace elements by their chelating effect and also enhances the absorption of other trace minerals (Sugiura *et al.*, 1998).

Proteolytic enzymes are stimulated by CA which leads to increase the feed intake, reduces the activity of microbes including ammonia and also has the capacity to reduce the risks of subclinical infections (Chowdhury *et al.*, 2009; Ou *et al.*, 2013).

Objectives of this study

The aim of present study was to investigate the whole body antioxidant status of silver carp fingerlings fed acidified diets

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Experiment was performed in Fish Nutrition Laboratory, Department of Zoology, Wildlife and Fisheries, University of Agriculture, Faisalabad.

Fish and experimental condition

Before onset the experiment, silver carp fingerlings were obtained from Government Fish Seed Hatchery, Faisalabad. For acclimatization to indoor conditions, fish were placed for two weeks in tiled tanks (1000 L). During this period basal diet was given for 6 days (Allan & Rowland, 1992) to fish. For feeding trial, 9 species of fish with same initial weight (3.526±0.0056 g) were kept in V shaped tanks (70L). Throughout this time, fingerlings were fed of that basic food once a time in a

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day. For each test diet experiment repeated three times. Feeding trial sustained for two months. During the study period, Jenway pH meter 3510 and DO 970 were used to monitor changings in water quality, specially dissolved oxygen, temperature and pH. All water tanks are inflated by capillary system around the clock.

Feed Ingredients and Experimental Diets

Feed Ingredients and feed stuff obtained from local poultry market and composition of chemical analysis was done by using standard methods (AOAC, 1995). Before incorporating feeding trial, the constituents of food were crushed and filtered to achieve the desired particle size (Table I).

The method for pretreatment of ingredients, 1 kg of the ground constituents such as fish meal, wheat flour, sunflower meal, corn gluten meal and 1.5L of distilled water was adding for made paste and retained it for 38 °C for 16 h and then dried. All dry ingredients were mixed for 15 minutes in an electric mixture. Though continuously stirring, then gradually add mineral mixture, vitamin premix and fish oil.

Five trial diets were made by using various supplementing organic acids at level of 2%. The D₁ contains no supplemented organic acids, while D₂ contain malic acid, D₃ citric acid, D₄ formic acid and D₅ lactic acid, correspondingly. To prepare appropriate dough for each trial feed, slowly mix 10% to 15% water. To make floating particles, then further process it via a laboratory extruder. After particles are dried, they are crushed and sieved to the desired size. Keep the pellets in the refrigerator at -18 °C until the feeding test is completed.

Ingredient	Percentage
Fishmeal	25
Sunflower meal	20
Soybean meal	10
Corn gluten meal	15
Fish oil	7
Rice Polish	10
Wheat flour	9
Mineral mixture**	1
Vitamin premix*	1
Organic acid	2
Total	100

Feeding Procedure and Sample Collection

For experimental feeding trial, the fingerlings were fed of their suggested diet. After feeding time of three hours, the extra food was exhausted by opening the tank valve. Wash water tank thoroughly to eliminate particles from the food then fill-up the water. Afterwards, return the fish to the fish tank. After the two-hour interval, feces were collected in beaker by opening valves of tank. In an oven at 60°C, each of the repeatedly processed feces was dried. Then ground and stored for chemical inquiry. For each repeated sample, the trial was continued to collect 5 g of feces.

Chemical analysis of feed

With help of pestle and mortar fish samples and diet were standardized Methods for determining moisture was: drying in an oven at 105°C for 12 hours, micro Kjeldahl apparatus used for measuring crude protein. By Soxhlet system, crude fat through petroleum ether extraction method determined (Bligh & Dyer, 1959) and in an electric furnace for 12 hours crude fiber measured (Table II)

Table 2: Chemical composition (%) of experimental diet

Diet	Organic acids	DM (%)	CP (%)	CF (%)	Ash (%)
D ₁	Control	89.49	31.11	9.05	9.95
D ₂	Malic acid	90.1	30.51	9.1	9.62
D ₃	Citric acid	90.17	31.071	9.045	9.8
D ₄	Formic acid	89.63	31.12	8.94	9.78
D ₅	Lactic acid	90.11	30.84	9.16	9.86

Figure 1: Modified UA system showing steel tank and main pipe

Figure 2: Modified UA System showing valve I and valve II and collection tube

Determination of antioxidant enzymes

Preparation of enzyme extract

Whole body was taken and rinsed with phosphate buffer of pH 6.5 (0.2 M) and homogenized in cold buffer (1:4 w/v) using a blender. After the homogenization, organ homogenates were centrifuged for 15 minutes at 10,000 rpm and 4°C. After centrifugation process, clear supernatants were stored at 80°C for enzyme assay while residue was discarded.

Enzyme Assay of Superoxide dismutase

The activity of superoxide dismutase was determined

by measuring its ability to inhibit the photo reduction of Nitrobluetetrazolium (NBT) following the method of Giannopolitis and Ries (1997).

Procedure

1 ml buffer was taken in cuvette as blank and inserted into spectrophotometer to note the readings of blank, after taking reading spectrophotometer was adjusted at zero at A560 nm. Then 5-6 cuvettes were taken and set them in a light box with an internally mounted light bulb of 30 Watt. Firstly 1 ml of buffer was added to each cuvette, then 0.05 ml enzyme extract and 0.016 ml of riboflavin was added in each cuvette. All the cuvettes were incubated in light box for 12 minutes. The cuvettes were transferred to the spectrophotometer, where 0.067 ml of EDTA/NaCN solution and 0.033 ml of NBT was added to the illuminated reaction mixture. The absorbance was noted after 20 s of reaction. Activity of superoxide dismutase was determined by measuring the % age inhibition of NBT.

$$\%age\ inhibition = \frac{Blank\ (Abs) - Sample\ (Abs)}{Blank\ (Abs)} \times 100$$

Enzyme Assay of Catalase and Glutathione Peroxidase

The activity of peroxidase was determined by measuring its ability to reduce the concentration of H₂O₂ at A470 nm (Civello *et al.*, 1995).

Procedure

A cuvette containing the 2 ml of blank solution was inserted into the spectrophotometer and set it to zero at wavelength of 240 nm. Then a cuvette containing buffered substrate solution was put into the spectrophotometer and initiation of reaction was occurred by adding 0.05 ml of enzyme extract the initiation of reaction was occurred. The reaction time is 3 minutes and noted the absorbance after interval of 1 minute.

Calculation

$$Activity\ (Units/ml) = \frac{\Delta A/min \times dilution \times 2\ ml}{0.04mM^{-1}cm^{-1} \times 0.05\ ml}$$

Statistical Analysis

Finally, data regarding the activities of antioxidant enzymes of whole body were subjected to one-way analysis of variance following Steel *et al.* (1996). The differences among means were compared by Tukey’s Honestly Significant Difference Test and considered significant at (p<0.05) (Snedecor and Conhran, 1991). Costate Computer Software, Version 6.303 was used for statistical analysis.

RESULTS

Superoxide dismutase status (U/mg protein) in whole body of silver carp fingerlings

Effect of different organic acids on whole body superoxide dismutase status in silver carp fingerlings is shown in table III. Data showed that acidification of

diet significantly decreased the activity of SOD in whole body of silver carp fingerlings. Furthermore, maximum value was observed in formic acid while, minimum value was recorded in malic acid among different organic acid groups.

Table 3: Effect of supplementation of different organic acids on superoxide dismutase status (U/mg protein) in whole body of silver carp fingerlings

Diet	Organic acid	SOD
D ₁	Control	4.55 ^a
D ₂	Malic acid	3.65 ^c
D ₃	Citric acid	3.83 ^{bc}
D ₄	Formic acid	4.10 ^b
D ₅	Lactic acid	4.02 ^b
PSE		0.068
P-value		0.0018**

Data are means of three replicates, P<0.05 Organic acids

PSE = pooled SE = $\sqrt{MSE/n}$ (where MSE= mean-squared error)

Catalase status (U/mg protein) in whole body of silver carp fingerlings

Effect of different organic acids on whole body catalase status in silver carp fingerlings is shown in table IV. Data showed that acidification of diet significantly decreased the activity of CAT in whole body of silver carp fingerlings. Furthermore, maximum value was observed in malic acid while, minimum value was recorded in lactic acid among different organic acid groups.

Table 4: Effect of supplementation of different organic acids on catalase status (U/mg protein) in whole body of silver carp fingerlings

Diet	Organic acid	CAT
D ₁	Control	65.66 ^a
D ₂	Malic acid	58.52 ^b
D ₃	Citric acid	53.22 ^c
D ₄	Formic acid	50.72 ^c
D ₅	Lactic acid	50.05 ^c
PSE		1.427
P-value		0.0025**

Data are means of three replicates, P<0.05 Organic acids

PSE = pooled SE = $\sqrt{MSE/n}$ (where MSE= mean-squared error)

Glutathione peroxidase status (mU/mg protein) in whole body of silver carp fingerlings

Effect of different organic acids on whole body glutathione peroxidase status in silver carp fingerlings is shown in table V. Data showed that acidification of diet significantly decreased the activity of GPX in whole body of silver carp fingerlings. Furthermore, maximum value was observed in citric acid while, minimum value was recorded in formic acid among different organic acid groups.

Table 5: Effect of supplementation of different organic acids on glutathione peroxidase status (mU/mg protein) in whole body of silver carp fingerlings

Diet	Organic acid	GPX
D ₁	Control	75.82 ^a
D ₂	Malic acid	70.11 ^b
D ₃	Citric acid	71.46 ^b
D ₄	Formic acid	68.27 ^b
D ₅	Lactic acid	71.39 ^b
PSE		0.904
P-value		0.0149*

Data are means of three replicates, $P < 0.05$ Organic acids

PSE = pooled SE = $\sqrt{MSE/n}$ (where MSE = mean-squared error)

DISCUSSION

Currently, there is considerable interest in the commercial use of organic acids in fish diets, both to control disease and to enhance growth performance. Researches have reported that several organic acids, their salts or mixtures thereof can improve growth, feed utilization and disease resistance in fish (Baruah *et al.* 2007; Hossain, Pandey & Satoh 2007; Sarker, Satoh & Kiron 2007; Luckstadt 2008). Hormones, antibiotics, ionospheres and some salts are most commonly used as growth promoters to increase the productive performance of fish (Fuller, 1992; Go'ngora, 1998; Klaenhammer and Kullen, 1999). Antibiotic growth promoters are used in fish diets as feed additives to favor growth and environment friendly aquaculture. However, it is necessary to make use of these antibiotic growth promoters in less amount as feed additive in fish diets worldwide to enhance the development of cross resistances to humans. However, the supplementation of organic acid is beneficial to replace the feed additives.

(Kim *et al.* 2006) investigated that organic acid supplemented diet can improve the growth and performance of fishes. Fish feed industry has been using organic acids for decades where most extensively used acidifiers contain lactic, citric, fumaric and formic acid.

(Baruah *et al.* 2007) designed a factorial experiment to study the effect of dietary microbial phytase, citric acid and their interactions on growth performance of *Labeo rohita* juveniles. Hence, it is suggested that phytase and citric acid act synergistically to improve growth performance and nutrient digestibility of *L. rohita* juveniles.

(Hossain *et al.* 2007) conducted a feeding experiment to investigate the effects of organic acids on the growth and phosphorus utilization in fish. Therefore, it can be concluded from these results that organic acids can play an important role in development of highly required eco-friendly diets.

(Pandey & Satoh 2008) observed phosphorus (P) and nitrogen (N) retention in rainbow trout fed on low fish meal based diets supplemented with organic acid. Hence, results conclude that low fishmeal based diets may prove beneficial for growth of rainbow trout if supplemented with certain organic acids.

Phromkunthong *et al.* (2010) determined the combined effect of citric acid and microbial phytase on phosphorus utilization. *Cyprinus carpio* fingerlings were treated with citric acid and phytase for 60 days. It can be concluded that positive effects of phytase can be achieved by adding low dose of citric acid.

CONCLUSION

Findings of experiment are as follows:

- Supplementation of organic acids significantly ($p < 0.05$) decreased the whole body superoxide dismutase activity (U/mg protein) in silver carp fingerlings.
 - Supplementation of organic acids significantly ($p < 0.05$) decreased the whole body catalase activity (U/mg protein) in silver carp fingerlings.
 - Supplementation of organic acids significantly ($p < 0.05$) decreased the whole body glutathione peroxidase activity (mU/mg protein) in silver carp fingerlings.
- In conclusion, supplementation of organic acids decreased the antioxidant enzymes in silver carp fingerlings.

Authors Contribution

K.R planed, did experiments and wrote manuscript. T.D, S.A, M.A and S.A helped in experimental work.

REFERENCES

- A. O. A. C. (1995). Association of Official Analytical Chemists, Official methods of analysis. 16th edition, AOAC, Arlington, VA. 1832
- Atapattu, N. S. B. M., & Senevirathne, T. S. M. S. (2013). Effects of increasing levels of dietary cooked and uncooked banana meal on growth performance and carcass parameters of broiler chicken. *Pak. Vet. J.* 33(2), 179-182.
- Baruah, K., Pal, A. K., Sahu, N. P., Jain, K. K., Mukherjee, S. C., & Debnath, D. (2005). Dietary protein level, microbial phytase, citric acid and their interactions on bone mineralization of *Labeo rohita* (Hamilton) juveniles. *Aquaculture Research*, 36(8), 803-812.
- Baruah, K., Sahu, N. P., Pal, A. K., Debnath, D., Yengkokpam, S., & Mukherjee, S. C. (2007). Interactions of dietary microbial phytase, citric acid and crude protein level on mineral utilization by rohu, *Labeo rohita* (Hamilton), juveniles. *Journal of the World Aquaculture Society*, 38(2), 238-249.
- Baruah, K., Sahu, N. P., Pal, A. K., Jain, K. K., Debnath, D., & Mukherjee, S. C. (2007). Dietary microbial phytase and citric acid synergistically enhances nutrient digestibility and growth performance of *Labeo rohita* (Hamilton) juveniles at sub-optimal protein level. *Aquaculture Research*, 38(2), 109-120.
- Boling-Frankenbach, S. D., Snow, J. L., Parsons, C. M., & Baker, D. H. (2001). The effect of citric acid on the calcium and phosphorus requirements of chicks fed corn-soybean meal diets. *Poultry science*, 80(6), 783-788.
- Chowdhury, R., Islam, K. M. S., Khan, M. J., Karim, M. R., Haque, M. N., Khatun, M., & Pesti, G. M. (2009). Effect of citric acid, avilamycin, and their combination

- on the performance, tibia ash, and immune status of broilers. *Poultry science*, 88(8), 1616-1622.
- Civello, P. M., Martinez, G. A., Chaves, A. R., & Anon, M. C. (1995). Peroxidase from strawberry fruit (*Fragaria ananassa* Duch.) partial purification and determination of some properties. *Journal of agricultural and food chemistry*, 43(10), 2596-2601.
- Papadoyianis, E. D. (2007). Insects offer a promising solution to the protein bottleneck. *Feed Technology Update*, 2(6), 158.
- Fuller, R., & Fuller, R. (1992). History and development of probiotics. *Probiotics: The scientific basis*, 1-8.
- GAFRD (2007). General Authority for Fish Resources Development Fishery statistic report. Egyptian Ministry of Aquaculture.
- Giannopolitis, C. N., & Ries, S. K. (1977). Superoxide dismutases: II. Purification and quantitative relationship with water-soluble protein in seedlings. *Plant physiology*, 59(2), 315-318.
- Góngora, C. M. (1998). Mecanismos de resistencia bacteriana ante la medicina actual. *Barcenola: McGraw-Hill*, 30.
- Hossain, M. A., Pandey, A., & Satoh, S. (2007). Effects of organic acids on growth and phosphorus utilization in red sea bream *Pagrus major*. *Fisberies science*, 73, 1309-1317.
- Jongbloed, A. W. (1987). Phosphorus in the feeding of pigs: Effect of diet on the absorption and retention of phosphorus by growing pigs. *Wageningen University and Research*.
- Kim, D. H., & Austin, B. (2006). Innate immune responses in rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*, Walbaum) induced by probiotics. *Fish & shellfish immunology*, 21(5), 513-524.
- Klaenhammer, T. R., & Kullen, M. J. (1999). Selection and design of probiotics. *International journal of food microbiology*, 50(1-2), 45-57.
- Lückstädt, C. (2006). Use of organic acids as feed additives—sustainable aquaculture production the non-antibiotic way. *Int Aquafeed*, 9(2), 21-26.
- Lückstädt, C. (2008). The use of acidifiers in fish nutrition. *CABI Reviews*, 8. <https://doi.org/10.1079/PAVSNNR20083044>
- Ou, C., Shi, N., Pan, Q., Tian, D., Zeng, W., & He, C. (2013). Therapeutic efficacy of the combined extract of herbal medicine against Infectious Bursal Disease in chickens. *Pakistan Veterinary Journal*, 33(3).
- Pandey, A., & Satoh, S. (2008). Effects of organic acids on growth and phosphorus utilization in rainbow trout *Oncorhynchus mykiss*. *Fisberies science*, 74, 867-874.
- Phromkunthong, W., Nuntapong, N., & Gabaudan, J. (2010). Interaction of phytase RONOZYME? P (L) and citric acid on the utilization of phosphorus by common carp (*Cyprinus carpio*). *Sonklanakarin Journal of Science and Technology*, 32(6), 547.
- Ravindran, V., & Kornegay, E. T. (1993). Acidification of weaner pig diets: a review. *Journal of the Science of Food and Agriculture*, 62(4), 313-322.
- Sakata, T., Adachi, M., Hashida, M., Sato, N., & Kojima, T. (1995). Effect of n-butyric acid on epithelial cell proliferation of pig colonic mucosa in short-term culture. *Deutsche Tierärztliche Wochenschrift*, 102(4), 163-164.
- Sarker, M. S. A., Satoh, S., & Kiron, V. (2007). Inclusion of citric acid and/or amino acid-chelated trace elements in alternate plant protein source diets affects growth and excretion of nitrogen and phosphorus in red sea bream *Pagrus major*. *Aquaculture*, 262(2-4), 436-443.
- Sarker, M. S. A., Satoh, S., Kamata, K., Haga, Y., & Yamamoto, Y. (2012). Supplementation effect (s) of organic acids and/or lipid to plant protein based diets on juvenile yellowtail, *Seriola quinqueradiata* Temminck et Schlegel 1845, growth and, nitrogen and phosphorus excretion. *Aquaculture Research*, 43(4), 538-545.
- Sing, K. W., Kamarudin, M. S., Wilson, J. J., & Sofian-Azirun, M. (2014). Evaluation of blowfly (*Chrysomya megacephala*) maggot meal as an effective, sustainable replacement for fishmeal in the diet of farmed juvenile red tilapia (*Oreochromis* sp.). *Pakistan Veterinary Journal*, 34(3).
- Snedecor, G.W. And Conhran, W.G. (1991). Statistical methods. Iowa State Univ. Press, Ames, USA.
- Steel, R. G. D., Torrie, J. H. & Dickey, D. A. (1996). Principles and Procedures of Statistics. 3rd ed. McGraw Hill International Book Co. Inc., New York. USA.
- Sugiura, S. H., Dong, F. M., & Hardy, R. W. (1998). Effects of dietary supplements on the availability of minerals in fish meal; preliminary observations. *Aquaculture*, 160(3-4), 283-303.